

CLOSED-FORM EQUATIONS FOR COMPOSITE STRENGTHS: FROM CONSTITUENTS TO STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY

Closed-form equations for calculating progressive failure strengths of a laminated composite by using its constituent properties and laminate geometric parameters are available based on the micromechanics bridging model. Through a user-subroutine UGENS, the bridging model theory has been incorporated into ABAQUS to define elemental instantaneous stiffness matrix and to capture ultimate strength of a structure made of or containing composite laminates. An alternative approach to the bridging model is presented in terms of Mori-Tanaka theory and Eshelby's tensor together with necessarily appropriate simplifications. Further modifications have been achieved by introducing a modified ultimate failure criterion for a laminate, a new material degradation scheme for a failed lamina, and pure resin inter-layers in between the lamina plies. The modified bridging model has been shown much more accuracy when applied to analyze the first World-Wide Failure Exercise problems. The correlation of its predictions with the experiments is even better than that of any other theory predictions taken part in the exercise.

Key words: Laminate strength, failure analysis, micromechanics, bridging model, ABAQUS

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composites have been increasingly used in engineering structures due to their high stiffness and strength to weight ratios and other outstanding properties such as anti-corrosion behavior. In applications, structure safety is one of the key issues to be considered. In order to make a judgment on the safety of composite structures, knowledge of their strengths is necessary. Efforts have been made to the development of reliable methods to analyze the failure strength of a composite^[1]. A World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE-I) has been organized to judge predictive capacities of a number of the most well-known strength theories in the current literature^[1-4]. The exercise results indicated that the predictive accuracy of the current theories did not attain a level expected for most applications.

Bridging model is a micromechanical theory for composites developed by the author in the late 1990s^[5,6]. Closed-form equations are established to calculate internal stresses in the constituent materials and to analyze progressive failure strengths of a laminated composite including a braided or woven composite^[7, 8]. By using this model, the composite strength can be easily obtained from the level of constituent materials. Compared with a macromechanical approach, only limited properties of the constituents and geometric parameters are required, and furthermore the failure mechanisms can be clearly captured. Compared with other micromechanics or multi-scale approaches, all of the expressions and equations in the Bridging Model are explicit and no iteration is involved. Thus, a faster and more effective analysis can be achieved.

Further developments on the bridging model especially with application to laminate strength analysis with improved accuracy have been achieved in recent years. Incorporation of the bridging model with ABAQUS through a user subroutine UGENS for strength and failure analysis of structures containing laminated composites has been made. These are summarized in the present paper.

FUNDAMENTAL

In general, a unidirectional (UD) composite is considered as a transversely isotropic material. Taking a representative volume element (RVE), the RVE averaged stress and strain increments can be expressed as^[5-6]

$$\{d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i\} = V_f \{d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i^f\} + V_m \{d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i^m\} \quad (1)$$

$$\{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i\} = V_f \{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i^f\} + V_m \{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i^m\} \quad (2)$$

The average stress-strain relationships of the fiber, matrix and the composite are given by

$$\{d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i^f\} = [S_{ij}^f] \{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}_j^f\}, \quad \{d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i^m\} = [S_{ij}^m] \{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}_j^m\}, \quad \{d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i\} = [S_{ij}] \{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}_j\} \quad (3)$$

where $[S_{ij}^f]$, $[S_{ij}^m]$ and $[S_{ij}]$ are the instantaneous compliance matrices of the fiber, matrix and the composite, respectively. A key step in the bridging model development is to assume that the stress increments in the fiber and matrix materials of the composite can be correlated using a bridging matrix $[A_{ij}]$ via

$$\{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i^m\} = [A_{ij}] \{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}_j^f\} \quad (4)$$

From Eqs. (1)-(4), following fundamental relationships for the UD composite are obtained

$$\{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i^f\} = (V_f [I] + V_m [A_{ij}])^{-1} \{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}_j\} \quad (5)$$

$$\{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i^m\} = [A_{ij}] (V_f [I] + V_m [A_{ij}])^{-1} \{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}_j\} \quad (6)$$

$$[S_{ij}] = (V_f [S_{ij}^f] + V_m [S_{ij}^m] [A_{ij}]) (V_f [I] + V_m [A_{ij}])^{-1} \quad (7)$$

On the other hand, according to Mori-Tanaka and Benveniste approaches^[9-10], the averaged stresses in the fibers and matrix materials can be correlated through

$$\{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i^f\} = [W_{ij}] \{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}_j^m\} \quad (8)$$

where $[W_{ij}] = [C_{ij}^f] ([I] + [F_{ij}] [S_{ij}^m] ([C_{ij}^f] - [C_{ij}^m]))^{-1} [S_{ij}^m]$ (9)

In the above \mathbf{I} is a unit matrix, \mathbf{F} is an Eshelby's tensor, and \mathbf{C} denotes a stiffness matrix.

Comparing Eq.(8) with Eq.(4), a bridging matrix $[A_{ij}]$ can be given by

$$[A_{ij}] = [W_{ij}]^{-1} = [C_{ij}^m] ([I] + [F_{ij}] [S_{ij}^m] ([C_{ij}^f] - [C_{ij}^m])) [S_{ij}^f] \quad (10)$$

In the case that both the fibers and the matrix are isotropic, the Eshelby's tensor is explicitly obtainable. A thorough manipulation and simplification has been done, and non-zero elements of Eqs. (10) are found to be^[11]

$$A_{11} = \frac{E^m}{E^f} \left(1 + \frac{\nu^m (\nu^m - \nu^f)}{(1 + \nu^m)(1 - \nu^m)} \right) \quad (11.1)$$

$$A_{12} = \frac{E^m}{E^f} \left(\frac{\nu^m - \nu^f}{2(1 + \nu^m)(1 - \nu^m)} - \frac{\nu^f}{2(1 - \nu^m)} \right) + \frac{\nu^m}{2(1 - \nu^m)} = A_{13} \quad (11.2)$$

$$A_{21} = \frac{E^m}{E^f} \frac{\nu^m - \nu^f}{2(1 + \nu^m)(1 - \nu^m)} = A_{31} \quad (11.3)$$

$$A_{22} = \frac{E^m}{E^f} \left(\frac{\nu^m - \nu^f}{2(1 + \nu^m)(1 - \nu^m)} + \frac{1 + \nu^f}{1 + \nu^m} (1 - F_{2222}) \right) + F_{2222} \quad (11.4)$$

$$A_{23} = \frac{E^m}{E^f} \left(\frac{\nu^m - \nu^f}{2(1 - \nu^m)(1 + \nu^m)} - \frac{1 + \nu^f}{1 + \nu^m} F_{2233} \right) + F_{2233} \quad (11.5)$$

$$A_{32} = \frac{E^m}{E^f} \left(\frac{\nu^m - \nu^f}{2(1 - \nu^m)(1 + \nu^m)} - \frac{1 + \nu^f}{1 + \nu^m} F_{3322} \right) + F_{3322} \quad (11.6)$$

$$A_{33} = \frac{E^m}{E^f} \left(\frac{\nu^m - \nu^f}{2(1 + \nu^m)(1 - \nu^m)} + \frac{1 + \nu^f}{1 + \nu^m} (1 - F_{3333}) \right) + F_{3333} \quad (11.7)$$

$$A_{44} = \frac{G^m}{G^f} + 2F_{2323} \frac{G^f - G^m}{G^f} \quad (11.8)$$

$$A_{55} = \frac{G^m}{G^f} + 2F_{1313} \frac{G^f - G^m}{G^f} \quad (11.9)$$

$$A_{66} = \frac{G^m}{G^f} + 2F_{1212} \frac{G^f - G^m}{G^f} \quad (11.10)$$

where F_{2222} , F_{2233} , F_{2323} , F_{1313} , and F_{1212} are elements of the Eshelby's tensor giving by

$$F_{2222} = F_{3333} = \frac{1}{2(1-\nu^m)} \left[\frac{3}{4} + \frac{(1-2\nu^m)}{2} \right], \quad (12.1)$$

$$F_{2233} = F_{3322} = F_{2323} = \frac{1}{2(1-\nu^m)} \left[\frac{1}{4} - \frac{(1-2\nu^m)}{2} \right], \quad F_{1212} = F_{1313} = 1/4. \quad (12.2)$$

It must be pointed out that after submitting the bridging matrix defined by Eqs. (10)-(12) into Eq. (7) the resulting compliance matrix of a UD composite may not be symmetric^[12]. This is not acceptable in reality, and the bridging matrix elements must be modified. The modification is made by requesting that the resulting compliance matrix of a UD composite is always symmetric, and that except for only five independent elements all of the other elements are dependent. Let us choose A_{11} , A_{21} , $A_{22}=A_{33}$, A_{23} , and $A_{55}=A_{66}$ as independent elements, the other dependent elements must be determined through the following equations

$$S_{ji} = S_{ij}, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 6 \quad (13)$$

It is noted that only two of the elements $A_{22}=A_{33}$, A_{23} , and A_{44} are independent, and the other element should be obtained by solving the following equation

$$G_{23} = \frac{E_{22}}{2(1+\nu_{23})} \quad (14)$$

Determination of the independent elements will be illustrated for a 2D bridging matrix. A general form of the 2D bridging matrix is given by

$$[A_{ij}] = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & 0 \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & a_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

As a UD composite has four independent elastic moduli, there are only four independent elements in Eq. (15) which are chosen to be a_{11} , a_{21} , a_{22} , and a_{33} . The other element is found from the symmetry condition as

$$a_{12} = \frac{(S_{12}^f - S_{12}^m)(a_{22} - a_{11}) + (S_{22}^m - S_{22}^f)a_{21}}{S_{11}^m - S_{11}^f} \quad (16)$$

Intuitively, the independent elements would be A_{11} , A_{21} , A_{22} , and A_{66} given by Eqs. (11.1), (11.3), (11.4), and (11.10). However, the Eshelby's tensor was obtained based on the assumption that an infinitely long fiber cylinder was embedded within an unbounded matrix material. In reality, the matrix and fiber materials in the RVE of a UD composite have comparable geometries. This implies that the estimated properties of the UD composite using Eqs. (11.1), (11.3), (11.4), and (11.10) would be in error by nature. As such, the corresponding Eshelby's tensor elements should be replaced by other possible constants.

Taking the above and other facts^[5-6] into consideration, a set of independent elements are chosen to be

$$a_{11} = \frac{E^m}{E^f}, \quad (17.1)$$

$$a_{21} = 0, \quad (17.2)$$

$$a_{22} = \beta + (1 - \beta) \frac{E^m}{E^f}, \quad (0 < \beta < 1) \quad (17.3)$$

$$a_{33} = \alpha + (1 - \alpha) \frac{G^m}{G^f}, \quad (0 < \alpha < 1) \quad (17.4)$$

Comparing Eqs. (17.1), (17.2), (17.3) and (17.4) with (11.1), (11.3), (11.4) and (11.10) respectively, it is seen that only higher order smaller quantities are omitted. For instance, when $E^f=70\text{GPa}$, $\nu^f=0.22$, $E^m=3.4\text{GPa}$, and $\nu^m=0.35$ which may correspond to a glass fiber and epoxy matrix system, the resulting A_{22} given by Eq. (11.4) will be 0.5255 if the Eshelby's tensor element F_{2222} is replaced by $\beta=0.5$, whereas a_{22} calculated from Eq. (17.3) is 0.5219. Further modifications

can be made for the independent bridging matrix elements when the fiber material becomes transversely isotropic. An elastic-plastic bridging matrix is also available when the matrix material undergoes a plastic deformation. Details can refer to Ref. [5, 6].

LAMINATE ANALYSIS

Introduction of inter-layers

For a laminate made of multiple laminae, a rich matrix generally occurs in between two adjacent lamina layers. The effect of such rich matrix on mechanical behavior of the laminate is taken into account by introducing an inter-layer made of pure matrix, as shown in **Fig 1**. The thickness of the inter-layer is assigned somewhat arbitrarily, as long as it is thin compared to that of a primary layer. 5% of the thickness of a primary layer has been used in the analysis^[13].

Fig 1. Schematic of a laminate containing pure matrix inter-layers

Lamina failure

The classical laminate theory is used to determine the load increments shared by each lamina within a laminate (**Fig. 2**). Further, the stress increments in the fiber and matrix materials of the lamina are calculated using Eqs. (5) and (6), and the total stresses are updated simply through

$$\{\sigma_i^f\}_k = \{\sigma_i^f\}_{k-1} + \{d\sigma_i^f\} \quad (18.1)$$

$$\{\sigma_i^m\}_k = \{\sigma_i^m\}_{k-1} + \{d\sigma_i^m\} \quad (18.2)$$

Fig. 2. Schematic of a laminate analysis

The updated stresses are detected against modified maximum stress failure criteria^[5, 6]. If either the fiber or the matrix fails, the lamina is considered to have attained a failure status.

Ultimate failure of laminate

According to the afore-mentioned detection, there are four types of failures, i.e., tensile and compressive failures of fibers and matrix, respectively. Different failure mechanisms should have different effects on an ultimate strength of the laminate. The fiber tensile and compressive failures and the matrix compressive failure are generally fatal to the laminate, whereas the matrix tensile failure is not so serious^[13]. Thus, an ultimate failure of the laminate is considered to occur if any single ply fails due to the failure of fibers or due to the compressive failure of matrix. A tensile failure of the matrix will only lead to degradation in the overall stiffness matrix of the laminate.

As a matrix tensile failure does not result in an ultimate failure but gives to stiffness degradation, there exists a possibility that the laminate strains may become infinitely large. Hence, an additional strain criterion is necessary to detect an ultimate failure of the laminate due to a too large strain or deformation. It has been shown that this maximum strain value can be assigned as

12%^[13]. In other words, as long as any strain of the laminate in absolute value is equal to or greater than 12%, the laminate is considered to have attained an ultimate failure^[13].

Stiffness degradation

Again because a matrix tensile failure generally does not correspond to an ultimate failure, a partial stiffness discount must be employed. The discount is achieved by reducing the matrix modulus to a significantly smaller value as per^[13]

$$E^m = 0.01E^{m,0} \quad (19)$$

where E^m is the matrix modulus to be used to calculate discounted stiffness matrix, and $E^{m,0}$ is that before failure. It is noted that all of the other fiber and matrix properties are kept unchanged.

Numerical examples

The WWFE-I was completed in 2004, which gathered 19 most recognized strength theories for composites in the current literature^[3-4]. The organizers posed a total number of 125 problems to judge efficiencies of the theories. Those problems were classified into five categories, i.e., failure strengths/envelops of UD composites, first-ply failures of the laminates, ultimate (last-ply) failures of the laminates, stress-strain curves of the laminates up to failures, and general features of the laminate failures. The organizers ranked the theories according to correlations of their predictions with the experiments. It was found that the Zionviev's theory gave overall the best correlation^[3-4]. All of the problems are reanalyzed using the bridging model incorporated with the modifications given above (called modified Huang's theory). Results are summarized in **Figs. 3-8**. The results achieved by Zionviev and Huang (called original Huang's theory) in the exercise are also shown in the figures for comparison. It is seen that except for ultimate strengths of UD composites the correlations by the modified theory are all better than those by Zionviev's theory.

Fig. 3. Comparison of different theories' predictions for strength envelops of UD composites

Fig. 4. Comparison of different theories' predictions for first ply failures of laminates

Fig. 5. Comparison of different theories' predictions for ultimate failures of laminates

Fig. 6. Comparison of different theories' predictions for stress-strain behaviors of laminates

Fig. 7. Comparison of different theories' predictions for general features of laminates

Fig. 8. Comparison of different theories' predictions with overall accuracy

INCORPORATION WITH ABAQUS

Extensive use of laminated composites in engineering structures requires powerful tools to analyze them. Although a number of general purpose finite element analysis (FEA) software packages such as ABAQUS are available, the application of them to the analysis especially of nonlinear behaviors, progressive failures and ultimate strengths of structures made of composites is not so efficient. One of the main reasons is a shortage of an efficient inelastic constitutive module for composites in the material libraries of the software packages. However, the bridging model constitutive theory is particularly suitable to be incorporated with, such as, ABAQUS to serve as a material module. This has been achieved through a user subroutine UGENS^[14] when a composite structure is discretized into shell elements.

At each node of a shell element, there are 3 displacement and 3 rotational degrees of freedom. Each element can be considered locally as a laminate, and the bridging model incorporated with the classical laminate theory can be used to calculate an instantaneous stiffness matrix of the element, and further to detect an ultimate failure.

An incremental generalized-load and generalized-strain relationship of the element (laminate) is expressed as

$$\{dP\}=[Q]\{d\delta\}, \quad (20)$$

where $[Q]$ is an instantaneous stiffness matrix. The generalized and strains are updated simply through:

$$\{P\}=\{P\}+\{dP\}, \quad \{\delta\}=\{\delta\}+\{d\delta\} \quad (21.1), (21.2)$$

In the subroutine UGENS, an array FORCE(6) is used to store the generalized loads $\{P\}$ and STRAN(6) to store $\{\delta\}$, both of which should be updated *via* Eqs. (21) before returning back. An array DSTRAN(6) storing $\{d\delta\}$ is brought in by UGENS. After the stiffness matrix $[Q]$, which is to be stored in DDNDDE(6,6), is formed, the generalized load increments can be calculated using Eqs. (20). A working array STATEV(NSTATV) is used to store "state variables" such as internal

stresses $\{\sigma_i^f\}$ and $\{\sigma_i^m\}$ in the fiber and matrix materials of each layer of the element, which should be updated once every running of UGENS, whereas another array PROPS(NPROPS) is used to store all of the necessary parameters, such as constituent properties, fiber volume fractions, lamina thicknesses, and so on, for the bridging model to define constitutive equations and strength behaviors. The integers NSTATV and NPROPS are used to specify the lengths of STATEV and PROPS, respectively, which must be assigned as input data.

In reality, a composite structure may consist of many different laminates. Each laminate has its own coordinate system (**Fig. 2**) and can be discretized into an arbitrary number of 3D shell elements. By convention, the local coordinate system of an element is specified as the corresponding laminate system (x, y, z), which is not necessarily coincident with the global one (X, Y, Z) of the structure. Thus, a coordinate transformation between the elemental local and the structural global coordinate systems is necessary. The local coordinate system of each element can be defined using *ORIENTATION option provided in ABAQUS if necessary. Then, the lamination angle of each ply of the element can be specified, and the material stiffness matrix of the element (i.e. laminate) is obtained.

However, with the UGENS subroutine, the quantities passed in such as DSTRAN(6), FORCE(6), and STRAN(6) are all expressed in the global coordinate system, whereas DDNDDE(6,6) to be returned back should be given in the global system as well. This means that at the beginning of the UGENS the quantities passed in should be transformed into those in the local (i.e. laminate) system, and before returning the routine all the relevant quantities should be transformed back into the global system. Fortunately, ABAQUS has already provided an array BASIS(3,3) into the UGENS routine to accomplish the required coordinate transformations.

According to a coordinate transformation rule, one has

$$\{\delta\}^L = [L]\{\delta\}^G, \{P\}^L = [L]\{P\}^G \quad (22)$$

where the superscripts “L” and “G” refer to the local and global coordinate systems, respectively,

$[L] = \begin{bmatrix} [\lambda] & [0] \\ [0] & [\lambda] \end{bmatrix}$, $[\lambda]$ is the directional cosine matrix of the local coordinates in relation to the

global one given by the array BASIS(3,3). Because $[L]^{-1} = [L]^T$, one further has

$$[Q]^G = [L]^T [Q]^L [L], \{\delta\}^G = [L]^T \{\delta\}^L, \{P\}^G = [L]^T \{P\}^L. \quad (23)$$

As an example, let us consider a curved laminate, which may be used in a bone plate application, with a geometry shown in **Fig. 9**. The laminate is angle-plyed, $[\pm\theta]_{6s}$, where θ varied from 0^0 to 90^0 with 15^0 per step. For bone plate application, holes on the laminates are necessary. The laminate is simply supported at two ends. A schematic diagram showing the loads and end constraints is given in **Fig. 10**. A total number of 4,743 4-nodal S4R elements with 5013 nodes are used to discretize the structure, as shown in **Fig. 11**. The calculated maximum possible applied loads (a single load applied at one point of the edge) varied with the lamination angles θ are plotted in **Fig. 12**. From the figure, it is seen that the largest load sustainable was not by the laminate with a zero lamination angle, i.e. the unidirectional laminate $[0^0]_{6s}$, but by the laminate with $\theta=15^0$. This is attributed to the fact that the laterally applied edge loads also generate a transverse moment component to the laminates, the effect of which on the load carrying capacity is enlarged by the holes. For comparison, the ultimate loads of the same curved laminate without holes were also calculated and are plotted in **Fig. 12**. The calculation for the curved plate without holes was accomplished with $34 \times 164 = 5576$ S4R elements and $35 \times 165 = 5775$ nodes. An interesting phenomenon was that without holes the unidirectional curved laminate exhibited the highest load carrying ability. As an actual bone plate must carry holes, a non-zero lamination angle in between 10^0 and 20^0 will be most suitable if an angle-plyed laminate is employed.

CONCLUSIONS

The micromechanics Bridging Model with latest development especially with applications to the analysis of laminate nonlinear and strength behaviors is summarized in this paper. The best feature is that all of the formulae involved are in closed-form and only limited parameters of the constituent materials and geometric specifications are required. Comparison of the predicted results by the model with experiments for the WWFE-I problems has shown the model is very efficient. Incorporation of the model with ABAQUS through a user-subroutine is also highlighted.

Fig. 9. Geometry of a curved laminate plate

Fig. 10. Schematic diagram of loads and supports for a curved laminate with holes

Fig. 11. FE meshes for a curved laminate with holes

Fig. 12. Ultimate loads of curved laminate structures with and without holes varied with lamination angles

REFERENCES

1. Hinton M.J., Soden P.D., Predicting failure in composite laminates: the background to the exercise, *Comp. Sci. & Tech.*, 1998, 58: 1001-1010.
2. Soden P.D., Hinton M.J., Kaddour A.S., Lamina Properties, Lay-up configurations and Loading conditions for a range of fiber-reinforced composite laminates, *Comp. Sci. & Tech.*, 1998, 58: 1011-1022.
3. Hinton M.J., Kaddour A.S., Soden P.D., A comparison of the predictive capabilities of current failure theories for composite laminates, Judged against experimental evidence, *Comp. Sci. & Tech.*, 2002, 62: 1725-1797.
4. Hinton M.J., Kaddour A.S., Soden P.D., A further assessment of the predictive capabilities of current failure theories for composite laminates: Comparison with experimental evidence, *Comp. Sci. & Tech.*, 2004, 64: 549-588.
5. Huang Z. M., Simulation of the Mechanical Properties of Fibrous Composites by the Bridging Micromechanics Model, *Composites Part A: applied science and manufacturing*, 2001, 32: 143-172.
6. Huang Z. M., A bridging model prediction of the ultimate of composite laminates subjected to biaxial loads, *Comp. Sci. & Tech.*, 2004, 64: 395-448.
7. Huang Z. M., The Mechanical Properties of Composites Reinforced with Woven and Braided Fabrics, *Comp. Sci. & Tech.*, 2000, Vol. 60, No. 4, pp. 479-498.
8. Huang Z. M., Ramakrishna S., Towards Automatic designing of 2D biaxial woven and braided fabric reinforced composites, *J Compos. Mater.*, 2002, 36(13): 1541-1579.
9. Mori T, Tanaka K. Average stress in matrix and average elastic energy of materials with misfitting inclusions. *Acta Metall.*, 1973, 21: 571-574.
10. Benveniste Y. A New Approach to the Application of Mori-Tanaka Theory in Composite Materials, *Mech. Mater.*, 1987, 6: 147-157.
11. Zhang H. S., Huang Z. M., Study of the elastic-plastic mechanical behavior of fiber composites by micromechanics, *Acta Materiae Compositae Sinica*, 2008, 25(5): 157-162 (In Chinese).
12. Wang YM, Weng GJ, The influence of inclusion shape on the over viscoelastic behavior of composites, *ASME J Appl Mech*, 1992, 59: 510-518.
13. Zhou Y. X., Huang Z. M., A modified ultimate failure criterion and material degradation scheme in Bridging Model prediction for biaxial strength of laminates, *J Compos. Mater.*, 2008, 42(20): 2123-2141.
14. Huang Z. M., Inelastic and Failure Analysis of Laminate Structures by ABAQUS Incorporated with a General Constitutive Relationship, *Journal of reinforced plastics and composites*, 2007, 26(11): 1135-1181.